

Research Article

The Functional Outcome of Hybrid Total Hip Replacement in Contrast to Cemented Arthroplasty

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: Research was aimed at the functional outcome comparison of total hip arthroplasty in terms of cemented and hybrid for the pain score mean change.

STUDY DESIGN: Randomized-Controlled Research.

PLACE AND DURATION: Research was held at Rawalpindi in Benazir Bhutto Hospital and it was completed in the time of six months as it started from March and culminated in August, 2015.

METHODOLOGY: Groups were made of the primary and secondary osteoarthritis hip cases who underwent arthroplasty as Group A & B respectively hybrid and cemented groups for total hip arthroplasty. Both the groups were analyzed for their pain scale through VAS (Visual Analog Pain Scale) at the interval of four, eight and twelve weeks and any improvement in the relief of the pain was also observed, we also made the comparison of both groups for the documentation of pain-relief.

RESULTS: There was a significant low mean pain in the participants of A group as (62.67±10.48) in comparison to B groups they were observed with a mean pain as (68.33±7.92) at the interval of 8th and 12th weeks having respective significant p-value of 0.022 and 0.005.

CONCLUSION: It is found in the research that the hybrid total hip functional outcomes are better in comparison to the cemented total hip in respect of pain score and mean changes as observed in the score of pain in both the groups.

KEY WORDS: Osteoarthritis, Hip arthroplasty, Hybrid hip, Functional Outcomes and Visual analog pain scale (VAS).

INTRODUCTION

In this modern age total hip replacement is among lucrative surgeries. Hip osteoarthritis affects are above ten percent in the age of above sixty years. Hip osteoarthritis is presented commonly to the disability and pain in the aged patients, joint of hip is socket and ball of synovial variety. Normal hip joint is a complex combination of acetabulum,

vasculature and proximal femur accommodating the increasing bones[1]. The aim of the surgical modification is the revelation of pain release and function of restoring is known as arthroplasty. The replacement of head and neck femur and acetabulum is carried out in the replacement of total hip also considered as effective surgical

procedure for the patients affected by the progressive degenerative hip disease. An approximate of primary and revision respectively 168,000 and 30,000 are carried out per year in United States of America[2]. Patient satisfaction is reflected through the pain relief and improved functionality. Cemented acetabular fixation is less obstinate in comparison to the cemented stem combination and un-cemented acetabulum considered as “hybrid hip” also commonly employed as being popular. Scarce literature is available in this regard for the comparative research on about cemented and hybrid arthroplasty regarding pain scale through VAS.

METHODOLOGY

Our research was aimed at the functional outcome comparison of total hip arthroplasty in terms of cemented and hybrid for the pain score mean change. It was a randomized-controlled research held at Rawalpindi in Benazir Bhutto Hospital and it was completed in the time of six months as it started from March and culminated in August, 2015. Groups were made of the primary and secondary osteoarthritis hip cases who underwent arthroplasty as Group A & B respectively hybrid and cemented groups for total hip arthroplasty. Both the groups were analyzed for their pain scale through VAS (Visual Analog Pain Scale) at the interval of four, eight and twelve weeks and any improvement in the relief of the pain was also observed, we also made the comparison of both groups for the documentation of pain-relief. Sample was selected through probability method and included the participants of all age groups from both sex with primary and secondary Osteoarthritis hip arthroplasty. All the patients

having Septic arthritis, Neurological defects around hip, congenital defects and Neuropathic joints were not included in the research. Research was started after the formal consent of the participants and approval of the hospital. Benefits and involved risk were communicated to the participants.

Random number table groups were made and they were named as Group A and B, respectively Hybrid Total Hip and Cemented Total Hip groups. Group-A consisted of a cemented polyethylene cup having cement less femoral stem; whereas, cemented total hip consisted of fast-drying bone cement for the affixation of the bone. The arrangements of the implants were made through Bait-Ul-Mal for the deserving participants and other who could afford managed it on their own. A record was maintained for the hip pain, reduced hip joint motion, limp and limb shortening followed by a comprehensive physical examination including flexion contractures, limb length discrepancy, deformities and motion range. In the regular investigations gait was also assessed and analyzed. For the confirmation of the lateral and anteroposterior view diagnosis hip radiographs were taken.

The scoring of post-operative pain was carried out through VAS in the intervals of four, eight and twelve weeks for the investigation of the improvement regarding VAS pain scale to find the relief of pain and its comparison in both the groups in the score range of 0 – 100. Zero was low intensity of pain and 100 for the intense pain. Every participant was subjected to Harding’s lateral and surgery approach and surgeries were carried out by the Consultant Orthopedic Surgeon.

Table-I: Distribution of Gender and Hip Involvement. (N=60)

Detail		Group		Total	
		A	B	Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	16	12	28	46.67
	Female	14	18	32	53.33
Hip	Right	22	13	35	58.33
	Left	8	17	25	41.67

FIG-1: Pain Score Comparison between Groups With Respect To Follow-Up (N=60)

FIG-2: Pain Score Comparison Between Groups With Respect To Follow-Up For Male And Female (N=60)

Data Analysis: SPSS-23 was used for the data entry and analysis; mean and SD were also calculated for pain score and age in both the groups post-operatively through comparative statistics in the interval of four, eight and twelve weeks. T-test was carried out on independent group having significant p-value as (≤ 0.05).

RESULTS

There was a significant low mean pain in the participants of A group as (62.67 ± 10.48) in comparison to B group as they were observed with a mean pain as (68.33 ± 7.92) at the interval of 8th and 12th weeks having respective significant p-

value of 0.022 and 0.005. Hip arthroplasty was carried out on 60 participants, which were divided in to two separate groups with average age factor as (65.05 ± 11.78) years. Group B had a high median age in comparison to the A group respectively having 71(IQR=11) versus 55(IQR=13) with a significant p-value of (0.0005). In the total sample the male to female ration was respectively 28 males (46.7%) and 32 females (53.3%) as reflected in Table-I. There was no significant difference in the groups on the basis of gender division and significant p-value was (0.301). In the division of side of the hip 25 left

sided (41.7%) and 35 right sided (58.3%) as shown in Table-I.

After the fourth week there was no significance in the score of the pain in Group-A in comparison to Group-B and both presented the pain score at the end of eight weeks as (62.67 ± 10.48 versus 68.33 ± 7.92 with significant p-value as 0.022) and in the follow-up of 12th week the scores were as (46.67 ± 11.24 versus 62.67 ± 10.48 with a significant p-value as 0.005). An assessment of mean pain score was made at the end of 12th week which was significantly less in Group-A in comparison to the Group-B in males as (p-value =0.004) and in females (p-value =0.005).

DISCUSSION

Cemented or cement less total hip prosthetics was used primarily; as the name shows the it is glued through cement prosthesis to bone in the type of cement[3]; whereas, an implant direct fixation to bone was made with the help of osteointegration which is comprised of an implant that is cementless implant[4]. Hybrid hip replacement is actually the cemented and cement less combination. Cemented prosthetics loosening and components migration is counted as major disadvantage[5]. According to the research of Karim and his team, it was approved about the titanium implants favor for the total hip replacement due to the characteristics of osteointegration that is cement less[6]. Long term results were not predicted because of the short follow-ups. It is found on the outcomes of various research studies that cemented femoral component is better than the non-cemented method for short durations[7]. Our research included 60 patients with a mean age factor of (65.05 ± 11.78) years. According to Toossi and his colleagues, patient's age was in the range of 45 – 87 years having mean age as 65 years[8]. Because of the life expectancy in the past few years the aged population requires THR and the trend will rise with every passing day[9]. According to the outcomes of our research 28 patients (46.7%) were males and 32 patients (53.3%) were females, which is similar to the research of Phedy[10]. Chammout observed

predominance of female as they are at an increased risk of osteoarthritis severe in comparison to the male population which increases after menopause[11]. No significant pain score was observed in the groups after 4th week and the pain score were low in the cement hip arthroplasty and in the cement less group in the 8th and 12th week. Our results were developed on the short time results[12]. Wyatt observed a pain which was non-disabling in twenty-four percent of the cases in the follow-up after one year with the cement less femoral technique which showed a decrease in the pain as the time passed[13]. Long term follow-up is missing in the Indian and Asian research studies as in the absence of pain and in the incidence less pain patients were not in a habit of continuing their follow-up visits to the hospitals[14]. In terms of inflammation and non-inflammation improvement was observed in the total hip arthroplasty in comparison of the non-inflammatory to inflammatory cases[15]. Troelsen observed better function and less pain score in the male young patients who underwent hybrid or total hip surgical procedures which are same as our outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Our research found that the hybrid total hip functional outcomes are better in comparison to the cemented total hip in respect of pain score and mean changes as observed in the score of pain in both the groups.

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